

NUMERICAL MODEL OF GALVANIC CORROSION IN A POLYMER COMPOSITE CORE CONDUCTOR

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ABSTRACT

A numerical model of the galvanic corrosion in a new composite overhead transmission line conductor is proposed. This conductor utilizes a carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) load bearing core with an outer fiberglass barrier serving as a galvanic corrosion barrier. The core is surrounded by the current-carrying aluminium strands. The model simulates the galvanic corrosion between the CFRP and the aluminium, in case the barrier is compromised. The conductor geometry was simplified to a two-dimensional, coplanar model with the electrolyte thickness as a function of salt load and relative humidity (RH). The modelling was conducted through parametric scans of salt load and RH.

Numerical results indicate that higher salt load and higher humidity result in an increase in the total corrosion rate, but the effect is not linear. At very high salt loads, the total corrosion decreases due to the restricted oxygen diffusion through the electrolyte layer. This important finding would have been very time consuming to determine from laboratory experiments.

1 INTRODUCTION

Galvanic corrosion is an electrochemical process that occurs when two dissimilar metals, or a metal and another conductive material such as carbon fiber reinforced composite (CFRP), are in direct electrical contact while immersed in, or bridged by, an electrolyte such as saltwater [1]. The carbon fibers behave electrochemically like a noble metal and can induce galvanic corrosion in less noble metals such as aluminum [2].

Aluminum Conductor Composite Core (ACCC®) is a relatively new design of an overhead transmission line conductor. It has a mechanical load bearing core consisting of two polymer matrix composites (PMC): a unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) with an outer layer of fiberglass composite serving as a galvanic corrosion barrier. The surrounding helically wound aluminum strands carry the electrical current. This design is quite different from traditional transmission line designs (figure 1). Due to the higher mechanical strength and lower mass of the PMC core, low thermal expansion of the PMC, and the fully annealed aluminum strands, ACCC has up to twice the current-carrying capacity compared to a conventional conductor with the same outer diameter [3]-[6].

Another advantage of the ACCC conductor is the absence of galvanic corrosion in the intact conductor [7]. High voltage conductors are usually exposed to local environmental conditions without any additional insulating or protective covers or coatings. Traditional conductor designs have a known problem with galvanic corrosion between the galvanized steel and the aluminium that may drastically reduce the service-life in corrosive environments. However, galvanic corrosion can develop in the ACCC conductor if the fiberglass barrier is compromised, and there is CFRP-to-metal contact anywhere in the vicinity, for example in a splice or by protruding carbon fibers.

Galvanic corrosion of the aluminum strands could result in the loss of cross-sectional area and over-heating of the conductor, eventually causing its catastrophic failure in service. A finite element (FE) model was developed using the COMSOL® Multiphysics Corrosion Module simulating the galvanic corrosion caused by an environment containing NaCl.

Figure 1: Left) ACCC conductor with a hybrid composite core and fully annealed aluminum strands. Right) Conventional *Aluminum Conductor Steel Reinforced* (ACSR) conductor with galvanized steel wires surrounded by hard-drawn aluminum strands.

2 PHYSICAL AND NUMERICAL MODELS

2.1 Physical model

This study has focused on one type of damage to the conductor: a split in the composite core along the centerline (figure 2), simulating potential damage caused by over-bending. This breach resulted in a large exposed area of the CFRP. It also generated a realistic fracture area and a sample design with good repeatability. The fiberglass layer still physically separated the CFRP from the Al, and the necessary electrical connection was made through a measurement circuit. This sample design was developed by the authors for experimental evaluation of galvanic corrosion [8]- [9].

Figure 2: Left) Damaged introduced by splitting the composite core along the centerline. Right) Finished sample of ACCC with simulated damage.

2.2 Numerical model

The relatively complex 3D geometry of the damaged conductor was simplified to a two-dimensional model (figure 3). The model was simplified further by modelling only $\frac{1}{4}$ of the conductor; an approach that is common with symmetrical objects. This results in a co-planar geometry containing aluminium, the fiberglass barrier, and the exposed CFRP. The width of the modelled carbon fiber composite (~ 3.5 mm) is half the diameter of the CFRP section of the core and the barrier width (~ 1.5 mm) is the thickness of the fiberglass barrier. The effective length of the aluminium is calculated as illustrated in figure 3, by summing the interfacial lengths (the red dotted lengths) of the Al. A thin (< 90 μm) film of electrolyte is added to span the three materials. The thickness of the electrolyte layer is a function of the relative humidity (RH) of the surrounding air, the temperature and the amount of salt present on the conductor. At RH levels above ~ 76 %, NaCl absorbs water from the air and forms a liquid electrolyte, a process known as deliquescence [10].

Table 1: Input values and functions for COMSOL

Variable name	Variable	Function or value	Unit
RH	Relative humidity	[varying from 0.8 to 1]	%/100
D_NaCl	Salt load density	[varying from 0.5 to 7.0]	g/m ²
E_cond	Electrolyte conductivity	24.4	S/m
d_film	Electrolyte layer thickness	$D_NaCl/1000*0.0000000215$ $*exp(0.0603*RH*100)$	m
D_O2	Diffusion coeff. for O ₂ in the electrolyte at 20°C	1.97E-09	m ² /s
O2_solubility	Oxygen solubility in water	$0.0003*exp(6.59*RH)$	mol/m ³
Eeq_Al	Equilibrium potential, Al surface	-0.952	V
Eeq_C	Equilibrium potential, CFRP surface	-0.0605	V
ilim	Limiting current density based on oxygen diffusion through the electrolyte layer	$D_O2*(O2_solubility)/(d_film$ $* 0.00000259)$	A/m ²
i0_Al	Exchange current density, Al surface	0.004232	A/m ²
i0_C	Exchange current density, CFRP surface	0.0547	A/m ²
Ac_C	Tafel slope, CFRP surface	-1.4949	V
Aa_C	Tafel slope, Al surface	0.1307	V

The FE model was built as three rectangles representing the areas of electrolyte spanning the three different materials. The rectangles do not represent the materials themselves. The material properties and the two half-cell reactions were defined in the electrode-electrolyte boundary interfaces by their equilibrium potentials, Tafel slopes, and exchange current densities. The fiberglass barrier is defined as an insulator and does not participate in the process. Boundary 2 (blue) is the anode and represents the dissolution of metal from the aluminium surface. Boundary 8 (gray) is the cathode and represents the reduction of oxygen on the carbon composite surface. Corrosion damage is only occurring on the aluminum surface. The electrolyte is the same in all three domains. The electrolyte is only defined by its conductivity, which was set to a constant value of 24.4 S/m. All outer boundaries of the geometry except 2 and 8 are assumed to be insulated by applying a zero-flux boundary condition.

Figure 4: The finished geometry with boundaries and domains. Note that the figure is not to scale.

A mapped meshing was used for the model. Because the electrolyte layer thickness is so small compared to the length of the geometry, a negligible potential gradient was assumed through the thickness of the electrolyte and the mesh could thus be created with only one element in the vertical direction. The mesh was defined so the element was very small close to the boundary interfaces and larger further away.

The model was computed using two simultaneous parametric sweeps at RT. The salt load was swept from 0.5 to 7 g/m². The relative humidity was swept from 80 % to 100 % in 2 % increments.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF NUMERICAL DATA

The local corrosion rate of the aluminium is the highest at the edge adjacent to the fiberglass PMC galvanic corrosion barrier, as displayed in figure 5 for a salt load of 0.5 g NaCl/m². This is the location that is closest to the CFRP (the cathode), confirming that atmospheric corrosion is typically localized to the interface between the two reacting materials (in this case aluminium and CFRP) [15].

Loss of material occurs only on the aluminium (the anode) where the corrosion current is generated by dissolution of the aluminium. The corrosion current on the CFRP (the cathode) is generated through reduction of oxygen dissolved in the electrolyte. The CFRP is inert and its function can be compared to a catalyst. Figure 5 also reveals that increased relative humidity results in reduced corrosion at the interface, but the more widespread corrosion increases the total corrosion rate.

Figure 5: Local corrosion current density for a salt load of 0.5 g NaCl/m².

As illustrated in figure 6A by the average anodic corrosion current density as a function of relative humidity, the total corrosion rate increases with increasing relative humidity. Each of the studied salt loads resulted in a similar trend. 2.7 g/m² was chosen as the example because this was the resulting salt load when conductor samples were immersed in 0.6 M NaCl (3.5 mass % NaCl) aqueous solution (similar salinity to seawater).

Figure 6B indicates that there may be a shift in control mechanism at really high salt loads. At low salt load, the electrolyte layer is very thin and the main limiting mechanism is the high resistance of the electrolyte. At high salt load, the electrolyte layer is thick and the main limiting mechanism is the diffusion of oxygen through the electrolyte layer. In the extreme case of immersion of the sample, the galvanic corrosion rate is lower than in atmospheric conditions, which has been shown in [9].

Figure 6: A) Average corrosion rate for a salt load of 2.7 g NaCl/m². B) Average corrosion rate at 100 % RH.

4 COMPARISON WITH LABORATORY MEASUREMENTS

The results from the FE model for a salt load of 2.7 NaCl/m² and 100 % RH agree well with preliminary laboratory measurements. The FE model predicts an anodic corrosion current density of 6.8 mA/m² under these conditions. Nine physical samples subjected to the same conditions displayed an average anodic galvanic corrosion current of 6.1 mA/m² ($\sigma=3.2$). Expressed as average penetration rate, the FE model prediction is 46 µm/year while the measured rate was 42 µm/year ($\sigma=22.1$). The scatter in the experimental test was fairly large, which is typical in atmospheric corrosion [15].

The aluminium strands in these samples were treated with phosphoric acid to remove the thick oxide layer originating from the manufacturing process. When the oxide layer was left intact and the samples only degreased, the average anodic corrosion current density of eight additional samples exposed to identical conditions was only 0.86 ($\sigma=0.18$) mA/m². The almost 8-fold difference points to an additional limiting mechanism that needs to be included in further development of the model.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The FE model described in this work is the first numerical model of galvanic corrosion in an ACCC conductor with a compromised galvanic corrosion barrier. The results from the model agree well with our preliminary laboratory measurements. The model shows that the corrosion in atmospheric conditions is localized near the interface of the two reacting materials. The corrosion is highly localized at low salt loads, and becomes more evenly distributed over the aluminium surface at higher salt loads and higher RH levels. The model has also shown that for higher salt loads and higher humidity levels the total corrosion rate increases, but the effect is not linear. At very high salt loads, the total galvanic corrosion rate decreases due to the restricted oxygen diffusion through the electrolyte layer. This important finding would have been very time consuming to determine from laboratory experiments.

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